

ON THE RESEARCH OF MEANS OF EXPRESSION OF SMELL

Burxanova Mashxuraxon Muhammadovna

Senior lecturer of Fergana State University,

doctor of philosophy in philology

mashxuraxonburxanova@mail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10008257>

Annotation. This article analyzes issues such as smell, its expression through verbal and non-verbal means, emotional-expressive effect on the reader when used in works of art.

Key words: issues, smell, expression, verbal, non-verbal words, emotional.

In today's advanced science, it is promising to research new directions in each field. In particular, communicative linguistics, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics, cognitive linguistics are the focus of attention of all researchers in modern linguistics. Their interaction is united in the system of the anthropocentric paradigm. A joint study of the interaction between cognitive linguistics and pragmalinguistics expands our view of the cognitive process. Cognitive knowledge is at the top of a person's understanding of the world. In our opinion, perceptual metaphor has a special place in metaphorical research as a means of expressing the connection between the inner and outer world of a person. The tool that shows its importance is its reaction to external world events.

Olfaction is the branch of science about the language of smells that communicates with being and its elements in the non-verbal communicative system. Olfactory means serve as semiotic symbols for information transmission. We analyze this issue on the example of the olfactory metaphor. An olfactory metaphor usually describes the transfer of meaning through smell. Olfactory is one of the most important topics in Uzbek linguistics today, which has been overlooked by researchers. In world linguistics, olfactory studies have been studied by many researchers, in which researchers approach the analysis from the perspective of their mother tongue. In this sense, we aim to conduct our research based on Uzbek language materials. Olfactory means are one of the elements of the communicative approach system, and the research related to this system should be classified based on the principles of non-verbal semiotic concepts. Olfactory units are initially divided into natural and artificial smells as phenomena related to people's daily lifestyle. Odors emanating from existing creatures, things, articles, fruits, polys products, and various plants are classified as natural odors. Natural odors are divided into pleasant and unpleasant odors. As a result of the rapid development of science and technology, an artificial olfactory environment has appeared around people. In this system, the concept of artificial scents was formed. In all aspects of human life, natural odors have been added to artificial odors. Until now, in the works dedicated to the research of issues related to smell, special attention is paid to the distinction of terms related to the olfactory phenomenon. In our opinion, the distinction between these two concepts is related to the history of formation of knowledge and skills related to the field. When the concept of olfactory is considered as a phenomenon, general information about the field is implied. The term olfactory phenomenon is explained on the basis of the formation of scientific paradigms related to fields. In the field of philology, the use of such terms as

"olfactory phenomenon", "olfactory poetics", "olfactory codes", "odoric code" is noticeable in the research of this direction.

That's why the formation and research of the olfactory system paradigm initially goes back to their classification. According to the data, "...the classification of odors known to all belongs to K. Linnaeus, who in 1756 divides odors into seven classes. After 100 years, Zwaardemaker distinguishes nine classes of objects. It gives its first classification in 1895, and a revised version is presented in 1914. In the classification of product smells, the scientist distinguished ether, aroma, balsam, ambromusculus, garlic, the smell of soot, and nauseating and disturbing smells. Without taking into account this classification of the olfactory system, the history of linguistics does not include analyzes related to these issues.

Recently, a lot of attention is being paid to non-verbal means of communication from the point of view of various fields of knowledge. Nonverbal or paralinguistic means are non-linguistic means of communication. That is why they are considered as research objects of various fields. The concept of paralinguistics itself was brought into scientific life by the American linguist A. Hill in the 40s of the 20th century. In modern linguistics, interest in this field is increasing because non-verbal means represent the identification of a person's emotional state, his psychological state and national characteristics. There are a number of studies carried out in the field of paralinguistics in world and Russian linguistics. No matter how many researches there are in this direction, they cannot cover all the problems related to the field. Different approaches to such a research object will lead to the emergence of various new aspects in linguistics. In science, studying issues within one system with problems related to another system serves to open a new side of the research object. In the research conducted from the beginning of Uzbek linguistics to the present, the relationship of one unit with another unit or their correlative series has been studied with the paradigm of comparison. In the process of communication, information is exchanged through various means. These tools serve to make the communication process perfect and complete. That's why scientific literature uses terms such as linguistic and non-linguistic means, linguistic and extralinguistic units, artistic details that serve to convey information. In information expression, each system element receives its own expression load. The load of expression as a unit consisting of a semiotic structure has methodological-functional, pragma-cognitive, poetic-stylistic properties.

There are different opinions in the scientific literature regarding the issues related to means of communication or forms of expression. The communication process or communication system forms a complex structure with a variety of forms and means of expression. Therefore, the solution to these problems is solved by separating the object of research, correctly naming the means and forms of expression, paying attention to the tasks they perform, and performing such functions as dividing them into groups. The field that studies these issues is called communicative linguistics.

References:

1. Екименкова Д.П. Чувство обоняния как объект междисциплинарного исследования//известия СПбГЭТУ "ЛЭТИ", № 8/2014. – С. 100.
2. Котенева И.А. Номинация запаха во французском языке. Автореф.дисс. ...канд. филол. наук. – Воронеж, 2006. – С.18.

3. Давлатова Р.Ҳ. Ўзбек тилининг дейктик бирликлари Филол.фан.док. ...дисс. Тошкент, 2021.- Б.156.
4. Сафаров Ш. Прагмалингвистика. – Тошкент. 2008. – Б.154.

